

(3H, s, CH₃), 2.75–2.8 (3H, s, NH₂), 8.2 (1H, s, CONH).

Compound **5** was prepared by similar method, (80%), m.p. 178° (Found : C, 54.20; H, 4.50; N, 15.80. C₁₂H₁₂ClN₃O₂ requires : C, 54.23; H, 4.52; N, 15.81%); ν_{\max} 3 300–3 100 (NHNH₂), 1 665–1 645 (broad acyclic and acyclic amido C=O), 1 605 (C=O), 750 cm⁻¹ (C–Cl); δ (CDCl₃) 2.65 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.45 (2H, s, NH₂), 4.2 (2H, s, –N–CH₂) 7.0 (7H, s, CH), 7.4–8.1 (3H, s, ArH), 8.2 (1H, s, CONH).

1-(4-Nitrobenzylidenehydrazido)-6-chloro-4-methylquinolin-2-one (**6a**): A mixture of **4** (0.251 g, 0.001 mol), *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde (0.151 g, 0.001 mol) and few drops of glacial acetic acid in ethanol was refluxed on a steam-bath for 3 h. The solvent was then distilled off under reduced pressure and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (61.13%), m.p. 224° (Found : C, 56.20; H, 4.40; N, 14.50. C₁₈H₁₃N₄O₄ requires : C, 56.17; H, 3.38; N, 14.56%); ν_{\max} 3 350–3 250 (NH), 1 660–1 680 (acyclic amido C=O), 1 640–1 645 (six-membered cyclic amido C=O), 1 600 (C=C), 760 cm⁻¹ (C–Cl); δ (CDCl₃) 2.45 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.2 (2H, s, NCH₂), 6.6 (1H, s, =CH–), 7.4–8.1 (9H, s, ArH and –CH=), 8.2 (1H, s, –CONH–); **6b** (60%), m.p. 203°; **c** (60%), 204°; **d** (63%), 203°.

3-(6-Chloro-4-methyl-2-oxoquinolino-1-amidyl-2-(4-nitrophenyl)-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one (**8**): A mixture of **6** (0.4 g, 0.001 mol) and mercaptoacetic acid (1.0 g, 0.001 mol) with pinch of anhydrous zinc chloride in DMF was refluxed anhydrous ZnCl₂ in DMF was refluxed on a steam-bath for 8 h. The solid obtained was crystallised from DMF, (65.95%), m.p. 300° (Found : C, 52.30; H, 3.30; N, 12.20. C₂₀H₁₅N₄SCl requires : C, 52.34; H, 3.20; N, 12.20%);

ν_{\max} 3 350–3 250 (NH), 1 690–1 700 (five-membered cyclic amido C=O), 1 670 (acyclic amido C=O), 1 640–1 645 (six-membered cyclic amido C=O), 760 cm⁻¹ (C–Cl); δ (CDCl₃) 2.45 (3H, s, –CH₃), 3.2 (1H, s, CH), 3.5 (2H, s, –CH=), 7.0–7.2 (7H, m, ArH), 8.2 (1H, s, CONH); **8b** (66%), m.p. >300°; **c** (68%), >300°.

The compound **9** was prepared by the same method, (59.72%), m.p. >300° (Found : C, 59.00; H, 4.20; N, 9.80. C₂₁H₁₇N₃O₃SCl requires : C, 58.94; H, 4.24; N, 9.81%); ν_{\max} 3 300 (NH), 1 700–1 690 (five-membered cyclic amido C=O), 1 670 (acyclic amido C=O), 1 640 (six-membered cyclic amido C=O), 760 cm⁻¹ (C–Cl); δ (CDCl₃) 2.45 (3H, s, –CH₃), 3.2 (1H, s, CH), 3.5 (1H, s, SCH₂), 4.25 (2H, s, NCH₂), 6.25 (1H, s, =CH–), 7–7.2 (8H, m, ArH); **9b** (64%), m.p. >350°; **c** (63%); **d** (58%), >300°.

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